

Regionalism and International Diplomacy Challenges: Are We Heading toward World War III or a new Cold War?

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Abstract

Objective: This paper examines the evolution of regionalism and its impact on international diplomacy. It assesses the efficacy of regional and international efforts to uphold global peace and security, investigating whether current global strains could precipitate a major conflict, such as a new Cold War. By linking non-traditional security threats with regional integration strategies, this study contributes to the international relations literature, demonstrating how these factors reshape global diplomacy beyond a traditional Cold War framework. **Method:** This study employs a dual-theoretical approach. Realism is used to analyze state-centric concerns, including military alliances, power rivalries, and security dilemmas. Constructivism is applied to examine how regional identities, norms of cooperation, and diplomatic practices shape international relations. Case studies were selected to reflect both realist dynamics (e.g., U.S.–China rivalry) and constructivist dynamics (e.g., ASEAN's emphasis on regional identity and consensus). **Conclusion:** The study concludes that regionalism has fundamentally evolved, transitioning from state-centric alliances to multifaceted organizations that integrate economic, social, and security governance. It underscores the necessity of proactive and strategic diplomacy to manage contemporary transnational threats and prevent large-scale conflict. The future of international stability will be determined by the adaptability of regional institutions, the success of diplomatic engagement, and the global capacity for collective action. Thus, effective regionalism remains a cornerstone of a peaceful and cooperative international order.

Descriptors

Regionalism; International Diplomacy; Cold War Dynamics; Security Alliances; Preventive Diplomacy; Non-Traditional Security

INTRODUCTION

Regionalism, as defined by Yankson (2023, p. 333 and 338), involves the strengthening of political, economic, and cultural ties among nations within a given region to achieve shared objectives, such as political stability and economic cooperation. With advancements in international relations, technology, and economic conditions, regional alliances have expanded to address issues of security, environmental sustainability, and cultural exchange. Notable examples include the

European Union (EU), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and Mercosur. Yet, what remains underexplored is whether these regional frameworks actually mitigate the risk of systemic conflict or instead reproduce Cold War-style rivalries in new forms. For instance, while the EU promotes integration, Brexit revealed resurgent nationalism; ASEAN balances great-power rivalries, yet China's growing influence has strained its unity. At the same time, Mercosur pursues economic convergence but continues to face internal disputes that open space for external interference. These contradictions reveal that regionalism can function both as a stabilizing mechanism and as a potential source of fragmentation.

Building on Yankson's concept, Vöyrynen (2003, p. 25–28) categorizes regionalism into "old" and "new" phases, highlighting distinct stages in regional integration. While old regionalism was marked by state-centric, security-focused alliances such as the OAU and NATO, new regionalism, emerging in a post-Cold War context is more dynamic, prioritizing regional identity and coherence. Organizations like the EU and Mercosur exemplify new regionalism, where alliances address political, economic, and cultural dimensions beyond mere military or economic agreements.

As regional alliances adapt to shifting global dynamics, diplomacy becomes essential in advancing national and regional interests, as Wattie (2024) describes. Leaders employ diplomacy using various foreign policy tools—trade, sanctions, military power, and international aid—to influence the actions of other nations. High-level negotiations and everyday diplomatic exchanges, often managed by civil servants, enhance regional ties and navigate the complexities of international relations. These efforts illustrate how regionalism and diplomacy interconnect, as alliances like the EU, ASEAN, and AU leverage diplomacy to promote regional cohesion.

The relevance of effective diplomacy is also underscored by current geopolitical tensions, with Deutsch's (1983) analysis providing a psychological perspective on Cold War dynamics. Deutsch identifies mutual mistrust, relentless competition, and the arms race as sustaining factors for hostilities. Today, multilateral efforts—such as the Iranian nuclear negotiations and discussions on North Korea's nuclear programs—demonstrate a collective resolve to avoid a Cold War redux. The interconnected nature of the global economy further complicates isolationist tendencies, offering hope for diplomacy in mitigating regional conflicts.

In specific regions, like the Indian Ocean, the changing security landscape adds another layer to regional dynamics. Cordner (2014) emphasizes the growing strategic importance of this region and the instability that arises from power struggles among major actors, including China, India, and the United States. This shift from state-centric to non-state threats exemplifies Vöyrynen's new regionalism, where security is increasingly intertwined with regional identity and cooperation.

The insights of Buzan, Weaver, and De Wilde on regional security complexes help explain why certain regions become focal points of global tension. To illustrate this relationship, the next section examines the Indian Ocean, where shifting power dynamics among China, India, and the United States reveal how regional institutions mediate great-power competition (Vreÿ, 2010).

Building on this theoretical foundation, the following section applies Realism and Constructivism to concrete regional examples. These cases demonstrate how power dynamics (a realist concern) and shared identities (a constructivist concept) interact to shape cooperation and conflict. The European Union (EU), the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and Mercosur illustrate these dynamics in distinct regional contexts.

Non-Traditional Security Challenges

Climate change is a paramount 21st-century challenge to global security and development, characteristic of the complex, transnational threats that defy traditional state-centric views. Although international agreements like the Paris Agreement set the global stage, regional cooperation is typically where meaningful action occurs. Modern regionalism has shed its earlier state-centric focus, now combining economic, social, and environmental agendas with security concerns. This evolution demonstrates how regional organizations have become crucial to global climate diplomacy. They approach issues like climate change, migration, and pandemics as non-traditional security threats, cooperating not just for survival, but to foster economic competitiveness and social stability (Väyrynen, 2003).

A comparative analysis of regional blocs, the European Union (EU), the African Union (AU), and Mercosur reveals their critical role in shaping diverse climate change responses. The European Union exemplifies how regionalism creates robust frameworks for climate action. The EU's Green Deal illustrates how regionalism extends beyond borders: by embedding environmental standards in trade agreements, the EU exports its climate norms globally. This transforms climate diplomacy into a tool of geopolitical influence, pressuring partners like Mercosur to adopt stricter sustainability measures. From a constructivist lens, this reflects the EU's effort to project its identity as a 'green power,' while realists would note its strategic use of trade leverage to maintain competitiveness (Schmidt, 2017).

The African Union (AU) has strategically integrated climate action into its long-term development blueprint, Agenda 2063. The continent is focusing on its immense renewable energy potential, with AU-led initiatives like the African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI) aiming to mobilize 300 GW of renewable energy by 2030. This transition is supported by the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), which promotes sustainable industrialization. However, significant challenges persist, including political instability, inadequate financing, and a heavy reliance on fossil fuels (Gelot & Söderbaum, 2023). Nevertheless, AU regionalism provides a crucial platform for collective action, consistently advocating for climate justice in global forums.

Meanwhile, Mercosur embodies the clash between economic pragmatism and environmental responsibility: deforestation-driven exports sustain national budgets yet undermine regional climate diplomacy. This tension has already stalled the EU–Mercosur trade agreement, where environmental disputes trumped market integration. Realists interpret this as evidence that states prioritize short-term economic gains over collective commitments, while constructivists highlight how European environmental norms are reshaping South American trade politics (Ga-

leano, 2024).

These climate challenges are deeply intertwined with other non-traditional security threats, such as migration. In the EU, migration has proven to be a destabilizing force. The 2015 refugee crisis, which saw over one million asylum seekers enter Europe, strained social services, created political divides, and fueled the rise of populist and nationalist movements, even influencing Brexit (Fargues, 2017; Etiubon & Ibietan, 2018). This revealed deep fragmentation within the bloc and challenged the EU's unity as a supranational actor.

Migration is also central to instability across Africa, though its drivers often differ. The AU recognizes that forced displacement—caused by conflict, climate change, and poverty—remains a major challenge, with the continent hosting nearly 30 million displaced persons (UNHCR, 2023). Climate-induced migration, driven by droughts and resource scarcity, exacerbates tensions between communities (Brown, 2021). In this context, migration becomes both a symptom and a cause of instability, which is why the AU's Agenda 2063 emphasizes regional solutions, including coordinated refugee protection and cross-border security cooperation.

Similarly, the COVID-19 pandemic exposed profound global vulnerabilities and created an arena for strategic regional cooperation and rivalry. The BRICS nations wielded vaccine diplomacy as a key tool of international influence, with India and China distributing doses to challenge Western dominance in global health governance and reinforce South-South cooperation (Chisholm & Chissale, 2024; Huang, 2021). At the same time, the pandemic magnified geopolitical rivalries, particularly the U.S.-China blame game, which hindered global coordination and fostered "vaccine nationalism" (Alperovitch, 2024).

Together, these cases show how non-traditional security challenges are reshaping regionalism. The European Union (EU) leverages climate policy as a tool of geopolitical influence, embedding environmental standards in trade agreements to extend its global reach. In each case, regionalism acts as a bridge between global agreements (Paris Accord) and national policies, but also as a site of contestation where identity, sovereignty, and economic interests collide. This highlights the need to move beyond Cold War-era frameworks: today's most urgent security dilemmas—climate, migration, pandemics cannot be explained solely by military rivalry but require understanding the interplay of power, norms, and regional cooperation.

HISTORICAL OUTLOOK

Regionalism has played a crucial role in shaping international relations and security, particularly during the Cold War when the bipolar power structure led by the US and the USSR limited the autonomy of regional security frameworks. This period saw regional dynamics often dominated by the influence of these superpowers, creating a semi-global system where local security considerations were subordinate to larger geopolitical agendas. Following the Cold War, however, there was an increase in regional autonomy and the rise of regional powers, as Vöyrynen (2003, p. 28–29) notes, though US hegemony and global power dynamics continued to pose challenges for regionalism, particularly in Africa, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia.

In this Cold War context, alliances like the Warsaw Pact became central to the Soviet strategy to counterbalance NATO, as outlined by the Department of State (2017). Created as a political and military coalition among Eastern European nations under Soviet influence, the Warsaw Pact exemplified Cold War-era regionalism in which the autonomy of member states was limited. The Pact's dissolution after the Soviet Union's collapse in 1991 marked the end of an era where regional alliances were primarily designed for collective defense against Western influence and intervention.

Far from disappearing after the Cold War, the Non-Aligned Movement remains influential in today's multipolarity. India, a founding NAM member, still embraces non-alignment though now framed as 'strategic autonomy' to navigate its relations with the U.S., Russia, and China. For example, New Delhi has deepened security ties with the U.S. through the Quad while simultaneously purchasing Russian energy and weapons, reflecting a balancing strategy consistent with NAM principles. This indicates how non-alignment has adapted to 21st-century great power competition, offering states flexibility without full alignment.

The end of the Cold War reshaped global alliances and shifted the balance of power, transitioning from a bipolar to a unipolar world with the United States as the dominant superpower. This shift enabled the expansion of regional organizations like NATO and the EU, as Deutsch (1983, p. 5 e 28) highlights, welcoming Central and Eastern European nations into these alliances and marking an era of deepening regional integration. Additionally, emerging powers such as China and India gained significant influence on the global stage, challenging traditional Western dominance and necessitating new forms of multilateral and regional diplomacy to address complex issues like climate change and cybersecurity.

Vöyrynen (2003, p. 31 e 42) elaborates on how the EU's expansion into Central and Eastern Europe after the Cold War profoundly transformed Europe's political, economic, and security landscape. The enlargement process fostered greater economic integration and political stability, strengthening the EU's position as a regional power. Yet, challenges arose, including economic disparities, immigration tensions, and the growth of populist movements, which test the EU's cohesion. Despite these challenges, the EU continues to prioritize further integration and enlargement as a way to sustain its regional influence and stability.

Similarly, ASEAN's development since its founding in 1967 has exemplified the evolution of regionalism in Southeast Asia. NTI (2022) notes that ASEAN initially sought to foster stability and cooperation in the region through principles such as mutual respect for sovereignty and peaceful conflict resolution. The Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC) in 1976 solidified ASEAN's commitment to regional peace, setting a foundation for cooperation that would eventually include broader goals such as economic growth and social development. This approach has allowed ASEAN to adapt to changing global dynamics while maintaining regional cohesion.

Together, these examples illustrate how regionalism, from the Cold War to the present, has adapted to changing geopolitical realities. Alliances such as the Warsaw Pact and NATO, non-aligned frameworks like NAM, and the development of organizations like the EU and ASEAN

each reflect unique aspects of regional cooperation and security. The continuing evolution of these organizations shows how regionalism is influenced by shifts in global power, economic integration, and the need for cooperative approaches to address contemporary challenges in security, climate, and development.

PRESENT-DAY GLOBAL LANDSCAPE

In Europe, NATO and the EU anchor security and economic integration, while in Asia and Eurasia the SCO and BRICS pursue alternative forms of cooperation. This contrast suggests that today's multipolarity is shaped less by ideology than by pragmatic coalitions: NATO responds to Russia's military assertiveness, while BRICS promotes financial alternatives to Western-led institutions. Both approaches show how regionalism adapts to systemic rivalry, blurring the line between cooperation and competition. Mercosur seeks economic union throughout South America; the G77 assists developing nations in the UN; OPEC coordinates energy policies; and the G20 deals with international political and economic concerns. Baba and Erşen (2023).

Yoshimatsu (2022) argues that current regional blocks and alliances influence international politics, economy, and security through promoting international collaboration. Important economic blocs include the USMCA, a trilateral trade deal between the US, Canada, and Mexico; the EU, which unites 27 European countries; and ASEAN, which fosters growth in Southeast Asia. Mercosur promotes trade in South America, whereas the African Union seeks unification among its 55 member states. In terms of politics and security, the Quad strengthens Indo-Pacific security, the SCO and CSTO concentrate on regional stability, NATO guarantees member safety, and BRICS represents an explicit challenge to Western-led governance. Through the New Development Bank and calls for IMF reform, it provides alternatives to U.S.-dominated financial institutions. Unlike NATO, BRICS is not a military bloc but an institutional counterweight, appealing to states dissatisfied with Western dominance. This suggests that global order is fragmenting into competing models of governance, not just competing armies—a dynamic that echoes Cold War divisions in softer but still consequential ways.

As noted by Chisholm and Chissale (2024, pp. 2 and 13), there are multiple important ways in which BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) are challenging Western supremacy. Due to their substantial resources and populations, they possess considerable economic power on a worldwide scale, altering the dynamics of global trade. The New Development Bank serves as an alternative to Western financial organizations such as the World Bank and the IMF. BRICS reforms aim to represent a more equitable distribution of power in global governance. They also challenge Western cultural and technological dominance by expanding their influence through technological developments and cultural exchanges. BRICS attracts countries seeking varied relationships by broadening trade networks, encouraging South-South collaboration, and providing development funds with fewer limitations. Despite internal divisions, the combined efforts of BRICS indicate a move towards a multipolar world.

Gelot and Söderbaum (2024, p. 821 and 833) note that the African Union (AU), which was founded in 2002 and currently has 55 member states, is essential to advancing peace and stability in the area. Its main goals are to maintain territorial integrity and sovereignty, advance peace and stability, accelerate socioeconomic integration, and strengthen unity and solidarity among African nations. The Peace and Security Council, the African Standby Force, and the Panel of the Wise are components of the African Union's (AU) African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), which is intended to handle disputes. In addition, the AU works to resolve conflicts, maintain peace, aid in reconstruction after a conflict, combat terrorism, and advance democratic governance. It also arranges humanitarian aid and health crisis responses and promotes economic integration through programs like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

STRENGTHENING GLOBAL SECURITY AND ECONOMIC ALLIANCES

The United States-Mexico-Canada Agreement (USMCA) and the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) are pivotal frameworks promoting economic integration and global trade. Toro-Fernandez and Tijmes-Ihl (2021, p. 147 and 169) highlight that the USMCA, launched on July 1, 2020, updates NAFTA to enhance trade among the United States, Mexico, and Canada through market access and compliance mechanisms, intellectual property rights, and environmental and labor standards. Similarly, the CPTPP, signed on March 8, 2018, unites eleven Asia-Pacific nations to address market access, investment, and regulatory harmonization. Both agreements emphasize non-tariff trade barriers, regulatory convergence, digital commerce, and environmental norms, which are expected to influence international trade laws and standards, fostering commerce, investment, and economic growth.

China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) aims to enhance global connectivity by investing in transportation, energy, and telecommunications infrastructure, thereby strengthening trade and investment ties with partner countries. This initiative has catalyzed Chinese investments in manufacturing, energy, and real estate, leading to economic growth and job creation. However, concerns about security, debt sustainability, and geopolitical implications have emerged, particularly affecting strategic alignments among Quad countries. Khanal and Chang (2023, pp. 362 and 387) highlight that while Chinese scholars emphasize the BRI's developmental advantages, researchers within the Quad focus on its geopolitical challenges, resulting in policy restrictions on BRI projects and the exploration of alternative infrastructure initiatives.

These evolving trade frameworks and infrastructure initiatives are influenced by technological advancement, scientific progress, and heightened volatility in the post-Cold War era. The proliferation of nuclear weapons, as President Clinton emphasized, remains a paramount global security risk, complicating diplomatic efforts as nations address threats of nuclear terrorism and inadvertent escalation. Nuckolls (1995) illustrates this enduring challenge, noting Senator Sam Nunn's prediction that managing the risk of weapons of mass destruction (WMDs) would be a "top continuous national security challenge for the next ten to twenty years." The risks associated with nuclear proliferation among nations highlight the dual dangers of intentional and accidental

nuclear engagement, posing a unique threat to international stability.

Colombo and Lecha (2024, p. 8 and 21) explore how regionalism and diplomacy are affected by the geopolitical dynamics in regions like the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), where Gulf states' influence and the involvement of Russia and China increasingly challenge US dominance. Regional rivalries, notably between Saudi Arabia and Iran, coupled with internal conflicts in countries like Yemen and Syria, fuel instability and limit diplomatic efforts. Europe, particularly the EU, faces mounting challenges, such as increased refugee flows and extremist threats, that demand stronger crisis management capabilities. To navigate these complex dynamics, the EU must reassess its diplomatic strategies and reinforce its conflict-resolution mechanisms to better address emerging regional and global issues.

These challenges underscore the importance of non-traditional security threats beyond conventional military concerns. Peter Hough argues that while military threats remain prevalent, they are no longer the sole threat to global security; issues such as migration, cross-border crime, and cultural conflicts are equally pressing. Juma (2020) supports this view, advocating for solutions that are comprehensive and community-oriented. Successfully addressing these complex issues requires adaptive and inclusive approaches to both regionalism and diplomacy.

Indeed, internal conflicts, economic disparities, and governance issues add further complexity to regional stability and cooperation. Effective diplomacy is hindered by fragmented policies and a lack of coordination among stakeholders, while humanitarian and migration crises place additional strain on regional alliances. Addressing these challenges calls for a multifaceted approach that includes adaptable policies, flexible frameworks, and heightened cooperation between regional and global actors. Boukhars (2019) points out that the success of regional powers often depends on their capacity to manage internal problems, as nations aspiring to regional leadership must address internal instabilities, weak political institutions, and structural issues that impede their ability to take on leadership roles effectively.

Baral (2024, pp. 170 and 181) suggests several strategies to bolster regionalism and address complex security, cultural, and socio-economic issues, recommending a blend of constructivism, neorealism, and neoliberalism to understand regional dynamics. He advocates for public-private partnerships and participation in global forums to foster cooperation, enhance inclusivity by empowering smaller states, and establish policies that promote financial stability. Additionally, Baral emphasizes the importance of updating policy frameworks to address contemporary challenges, as well as strengthening regional organizations to manage new and emerging concerns.

Collaborative efforts within regional blocs are often undermined by economic imbalances, as seen in ASEAN where developed members gain more from schemes like the BRI. These disparities, which Khanal and Chang (2023, pp. 363, 377) argue exacerbate social tensions and impede global trade integration, pose a fundamental geopolitical challenge to regional cooperation. Addressing this requires a committed focus on sustainable development and equitable investment to bridge the inequality gap and build a more resilient collaborative framework.

As the global nuclear landscape becomes increasingly complex, with emerging powers such as China, India, and Pakistan developing their arsenals, Miller (2020) highlights that this shift from a binary US-Russia dynamic introduces new risks of escalation. The proliferation of nuclear capabilities in multiple nations amplifies competition and heightens the potential for regional and global tensions, diverting resources from developmental goals toward military expenditures.

Colombo and Lecha (2024, pp. 7–22) conclude that economic and social inequalities within MENA are significant barriers to regional stability. Discrepancies in wealth among Gulf states, alongside rivalry within blocs like the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) and between nations such as Morocco and Algeria, hinder regional cohesion. Policies that promote income redistribution, foster international trust, and support balanced development are necessary to address these inequalities. The EU's role in supporting regional stability through development initiatives and institution-building could help counterbalance internal divisions and foster more inclusive growth.

Finally, economic inequalities within and between regional blocs such as the EU, ASEAN, and the African Union (AU) continue to affect regional cooperation. Toro-Fernandez and Tijmes-Ihl (2021, p. 147) observe that wealth and resource disparities, compounded by security challenges such as nuclear proliferation and regional conflicts, hinder integration efforts. Addressing these issues calls for comprehensive economic initiatives, ethical trade policies, and diplomatic strategies that mitigate security risks while fostering cooperation and stability across regions.

Neither Realism nor Constructivism alone can capture the complexity of contemporary regionalism. Realism explains the structural constraints that drive competition, but it overlooks how identity and legitimacy inform diplomatic choices. Constructivism, in turn, illuminates the social processes that produce cooperation but often underestimates material incentives. By combining these frameworks, this study adopts a layered perspective: Realism defines the strategic environment, while Constructivism explains how actors interpret and navigate it.

CASE STUDIES:

- Europe: Integration vs. Sovereignty
- Asia: rising power dynamics (China/ASEAN)
- Middle East: intra-regional rivalries
- Africa: integration despite instability
- Americas: uneven integration (Mercosur)
- BRICS: challenge to Western-led order

1. Brexit:

Etiubon and Ibietan (2018, p. 34 and 36) highlight Brexit and nationalism as significant challenges to the European Union, leading to strained power dynamics and prompting the EU to reconsider its liberal policies. Brexit not only altered the European Council's balance but also introduced disruptions to the EU's cohesiveness, particularly in trade, financial, and regulatory areas. This

shift places additional stress on the EU, as nationalist forces in countries like France and the Netherlands gain influence, further threatening the Union's unity. Likewise, Schmidt (2017) notes that these strains are compounded by security threats, the refugee crisis, and heightened tensions with Russia, which collectively underscore the EU's struggle to maintain a cooperative strategy. The convergence of these issues raises concerns about the EU's democratic legitimacy and institutional resilience, sparking uncertainty over its future. Together, Brexit and rising nationalism question the EU's capability to remain a cohesive force in European and global politics.

From a realist perspective, Brexit represents a reassertion of sovereignty against supranational integration, showing that states ultimately prioritize control over security, borders, and trade when threatened by perceived external dependence. By contrast, a constructivist view highlights how nationalist identity discourses 'taking back control's reshaping EU legitimacy and weakening the Union's shared identity. In this sense, Brexit is more than a policy shift, it reveals how material interests and identity politics interact to fragment regional blocs.

Nationalism in Europe is not a new phenomenon, as various forms of nationalist movements have periodically emerged throughout the 20th century, often responding to crises and fears of cultural erosion. Before Brexit, countries like France and Hungary already experienced a growing nationalist tide, spurred by economic crises and immigration debates. Brexit has acted as a catalyst for these sentiments, emboldening nationalist parties across Europe. Parties advocating sovereignty and skeptical of EU integration gained momentum, viewing Brexit as a success in reclaiming national control. This wave has sparked debates on EU legitimacy and unity, especially in countries where anti-EU sentiment resonates deeply.

The consequences of Brexit and the rise of nationalism reach into the economic, political, and social fabrics of the EU. Economically, the UK's departure disrupts trade and market stability while the rise in economic nationalism across member states challenges the EU's principles of free trade. Politically, Brexit has amplified internal divisions within the EU, with nationalist movements threatening traditional political structures and prompting calls for reform to address citizens' concerns. Socially, nationalism has led to increased polarization, with rhetoric often targeting immigrants and minorities, challenging the EU's foundational principles of inclusivity and solidarity. The EU's future now depends on its ability to address these growing divides and adapt to an evolving political landscape that prioritizes both unity and respect for member states' sovereignty.

Figure 1: NATO, EU, Schengen and Eurozone member states in Europe

Source: https://www.reddit.com/r/MapPorn/comments/1bg22oy/nato_eu_schengen_and_eurozone_member_states_in/#lightbox

2. ASEAN:

China's rapid ascent has significantly altered Asia's geopolitical landscape, challenging the region's established dynamics and prompting diverse responses from neighboring countries. According to Pelaudeix (2023), ASEAN nations have strategically adopted hedging techniques to balance engagement with China while diversifying alliances. Institutions like the East Asia Summit and the ASEAN embodies a different form of regionalism: hedging. By engaging both the U.S. (through security dialogues) and China (through trade agreements like RCEP), ASEAN avoids choosing sides. This strategy reflects the legacy of non-alignment, showing how smaller states use regionalism to maintain autonomy in the face of great power competition. However, ASEAN's consensus model also exposes its weakness, as seen in its inability to address the Myanmar crisis, highlighting the trade-off between inclusivity and effectiveness.

Realists interpret ASEAN's hedging as a response to China's material rise: smaller states balance between the U.S. for security and China for trade, seeking to avoid domination by either. Constructivists, however, emphasize ASEAN's reliance on the 'ASEAN Way' consensus, non-interference, and regional identity as a social practice that tempers conflict and maintains cohesion despite external pressures. Thus, ASEAN demonstrates how regionalism can operate as both a realist survival strategy and a constructivist identity project.

The BRI, launched in 2013, is pivotal to China's foreign policy, aiming to enhance regional connectivity through significant infrastructure investments, such as railways and ports. While the in-

initiative brings potential economic advantages for participating nations, it also raises concerns about debt dependency and an increased Chinese influence over smaller countries. However, China's ascendancy is not without its challenges. Territorial disputes in the South China Sea have intensified tensions with neighboring states and the U.S., while ongoing trade conflicts with the U.S. and Europe over trade practices add to these complications. As China navigates these domestic and international challenges, including an aging population and economic inequality, its ability to maintain influence within Asia's evolving geopolitical landscape remains uncertain.

Figure 2: Maps of ASEAN Countries with their National Flags and Costumes Posters

Source: <https://www.ost.co.th/en/product/1914/posters-ep-492>

3. Gulf Cooperation Council

Del Sarto and Lecha (2024, p. 1447 and 1467) explain that six Gulf countries make up the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), which was founded in 1981 and initially focused on economic cooperation. However, the GCC also had a significant impact on regional security. Despite some early successes, for realists, the GCC crisis shows how rivalries for regional leadership (Saudi Arabia vs. Qatar) undermine collective security frameworks, with material power and strategic autonomy trumping shared institutions. Constructivists, however, see the rift as rooted in competing identity narratives: Qatar's support for political Islam versus Saudi Arabia's conservative monarchical legitimacy. The GCC's struggle therefore demonstrates how both hard power rivalries and identity fractures constrain regional integration.

Research on financial contagion has received a lot of attention, particularly since the 2008 Global Financial Crisis (GFC). According to early research by Engle et al. (1990), trade and financial ties are the means by which financial volatility is propagated. These theories are known as the "heat-wave" and "meteor shower" theories. Studies conducted in the MENA area show that there is little market integration among MENA stock markets, although there are significant links with developed markets. Financial Stress Indexes (FSI) have gained popularity as a tool for evaluating financial spillovers; they demonstrate that the GFC exacerbated spillovers and that MENA markets react slowly to outside information. Financial strain and oil prices have a complicated rela-

tionship; both before and after the Great Financial Crisis, there is evidence of bidirectional volatility spillovers. This underscores the necessity of additional research on the interplay between oil price and financial stress in the region, given their noteworthy influence on the GCC nations. Understanding these financial dynamics is crucial for GCC member states as they navigate economic challenges amid regional political tensions.

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) enhances regional security through its defense planning council and the Peninsula Shield Force, which are vital given the geopolitical tensions in the Middle East, especially concerning Iran. Joint military exercises and intelligence-sharing agreements strengthen the collective defense capabilities of member states. Politically, the GCC fosters dialogue and coordination, allowing for a unified stance during crises, as evidenced during the Arab Spring. Additionally, the Council promotes cultural ties and social exchanges among its members through initiatives in education and tourism, fostering a shared identity. Furthermore, substantial investments in infrastructure projects in transportation and energy sectors enhance connectivity and economic growth, benefiting all member states and contributing to regional development. These initiatives not only address security concerns but also aim to mitigate the economic vulnerabilities highlighted in the research on financial contagion, ultimately supporting the GCC's stability and resilience in a complex geopolitical landscape.

Figure 3: Gulf Cooperation Council Countries

Source:

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Map-of-the-Gulf-Cooperation-Council-Countries-Saudi-Arabia-UAE-United-Arab-Emirates_fig1_268880140

4. The Arab Maghreb Union

The Arab Maghreb Union (UMA), established in 1989, aims to promote economic integration and regional stability among Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and Mauritania by facilitating trade and coordinated policies, as noted by Colombo and Lecha (2024, pp. 8, 21). However, its effectiveness is undermined by internal rivalries, particularly between Algeria and Morocco, along with security issues such as political instability and Islamic extremism. This challenge is echoed in other regional organizations like the Arab League (LEA) and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), which similarly struggle with internal conflicts and ideological divisions that hinder their progress toward cooperation and development.

Political tensions, particularly the dispute over Western Sahara, have further impeded UMA's ability to establish a common market and unified foreign policy, despite some early successes in sectors like agriculture and transportation, according to DIFADI (2024, p. 226 and 230). Internal rivalries, along with issues like industrial inefficiency, climate dependency, rapid population growth, and high unemployment, have contributed to the UMA's stagnation. Addressing these challenges, such as harmonizing accounting laws, is critical for revitalizing regional integration and reevaluating the UMA's objectives and approaches.

The security landscape in North Africa has become increasingly complex, driven by the rise of extremist groups and the spillover effects of conflicts in neighboring regions like the Sahel. In response, the UMA has attempted to enhance cooperation through initiatives focused on border security, intelligence sharing, and joint military operations. However, the organization faces criticism for its limited operational capacity and political cohesion, with divergent national interests often hindering collective action. This perception of the UMA as an "invisible" entity in regional security highlights the need for a robust institutional framework and a unified approach among member states. To fulfill its potential in enhancing regional security, the UMA must address these operational challenges and foster greater integration among its members, contributing to overall stability in North Africa.

Figure 4: The Arab Maghreb Union

Source: <https://studies.aljazeera.net/en/reports/2015/01/201512713642692743.html>

5. The African Union

The African Union (AU), established on July 26, 2002, in Durban, South Africa, is a continental union comprising 55 member states and succeeded the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), which was founded in 1963. The AU marks a significant shift from focusing on liberation struggles to promoting economic development, political stability, and integration among African nations. Its primary objectives include fostering unity, defending sovereignty, and enhancing socio-economic integration across various sectors such as political governance, human rights, and security, while advocating for democratic principles and good governance. Key institutions include the African Union Commission (AUC) and the Pan-African Parliament. The AU's landmark initiative, the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), aims to create a single market for goods and services, enhancing intra-African trade and economic growth. The AU's vision is outlined in Agenda 2063, which focuses on inclusive and sustainable development, peace, and security, striving to transform Africa into a global powerhouse.

However, the AU faces numerous obstacles, including internal conflict, economic inequality, and security risks, as noted by Gelot and Söderbaum (2023, p. 822 and 834). Despite these challenges, the AU employs a comprehensive strategy to promote peace and prosperity across the continent. A key initiative is the African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), which includes the African Standby Force (ASF), the Panel of the Wise, and the Peace and Security Council (PSC) for monitoring and resolving disputes. Furthermore, through the AfCFTA, the realists view the AU's limitations—funding dependence, weak enforcement capacity—as evidence that regional organizations remain secondary to state sovereignty and material constraints. Constructivists, by contrast, highlight the AU's Agenda 2063 and the principle of 'African solutions to African problems' as a powerful narrative that builds continental identity and legitimacy, even when implementation lags. Thus, the AU reveals the tension between weak material power and strong normative aspirations in shaping regionalism.

H.E. Moussa Faki Mahamat, Chairperson of the African Union Commission, emphasized the need for a comprehensive approach to Africa's security issues, citing conflicts and humanitarian crises in Sudan, Somalia, and the Sahel. H.E. Dhoahir Dhoulkamal highlighted terrorism and political instability as significant threats to democracy, noting stalled political transitions in Mali, Niger, and Burkina Faso. Meanwhile, H.E. Taye Atske-Selassie praised the African Union's efforts in resolving the Ethiopian conflict and stressed the importance of effectively implementing Agenda 2063. H.E. Claver Gatete called for improved education systems to align with job market needs and leverage technological advancements. Additionally, the AU's G20 membership presents a key opportunity for global influence, with upcoming discussions focusing on trade, integration, and education, as noted in an African Union Press Release (2024).

Figure 5: The African Union**THE SIX REGIONS OF THE AFRICAN UNION****Source:**

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Regions-of-the-African-Union-according-to-the-African-Union-classification_fig1_363811653

6. Mercosur

Mercosur, or the Southern Common Market, is a regional trade bloc established in 1991, originally comprising Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay, with Bolivia joining as a full member in 2023. Its primary aim is to promote economic integration, trade, and investment among member states while enhancing political dialogue and stability in the region, largely as a response to historical rivalries, particularly between Argentina and Brazil. While Mercosur has boosted trade integration, realist perspectives suggest its uneven economic development creates vulnerabilities that external powers can exploit. In contrast, constructivism highlights how Mercosur fosters a shared South American identity that can mitigate conflict. Despite these successes, the bloc faces challenges such as internal divisions, economic inequality, and geopolitical pressures, which may affect its future viability. Security governance within Mercosur is rooted in democracy and human rights, with mechanisms for political dialogue and conflict resolution. Internal security concerns, such as organized crime and drug trafficking, alongside external challenges from major global powers, highlight the need for member states to collaborate on security measures. The interplay between security and economic development is critical, as a secure environment fosters investor confidence and trade, while insecurity can hinder economic growth and budget allocations for development programs.

From early 2022 to mid-2023, Pena et al. (2023) examine the achievements and obstacles of Mercosur's regional integration and collaboration. The member states—Uruguay, Brazil, Paraguay, and Argentina—despite their strategic differences, have made significant progress within the bloc. Notable achievements include advancements in the Common External Tariff (CET), a recovery in commerce and foreign direct investment post-pandemic, and institutional develop-

ments like the Structural Convergence Fund (FOCEM), as well as new agendas addressing digital and environmental issues. Additionally, biotechnology initiatives have progressed alongside extensive discussions with other countries on external relations. Nonetheless, persistent challenges remain, including internal disputes, unresolved issues regarding economic integration, and difficulties in signing trade agreements with external nations. Overall, Mercosur continues to strive for greater integration despite these ongoing obstacles.

Realists interpret Mercosur’s divisions—Brazil’s economic dominance, Paraguay’s tariff disputes as proof that states defend national interests when costs outweigh collective gains. Constructivists instead point to how Mercosur fosters a South American identity through shared institutions (FOCEM, Ushuaia Protocol), which help mitigate conflict despite disparities. The bloc thus embodies a dual reality: materially fragile but socially cohesive.

Galeano (2024, p. 61-63) highlights that Paraguay’s budget increased by 299,069,772,479 guaraníes in 2023, reaching 2,969,119,995,928 guaraníes, up from 2,670,050,223,449 guaraníes in 2022. However, customs revenue, essential for funding healthcare and education, was adversely affected by the CMC 08/2022 standard’s reduction in import tariffs. While customs collections initially rose, the tariff cuts led to revenue fluctuations, with some months experiencing increases while others saw declines. Overall, the reduction in tariffs contributed to decreased customs revenue, although import volume and commodity value also influenced these trends. The significant impact on public health expenditures and services necessitates further long-term analysis and comparative studies among Mercosur nations to fully assess the broader effects.

Figure 6: Mercosur

Source: <https://geopoliticalfutures.com/mercosurs-changing-trade-patterns/>

Usman et al. (2023, pp. 56 and 67) examine the economic and environmental challenges facing Mercosur countries, with an emphasis on energy consumption, natural resource management, technological advancements, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The report emphasizes the struggle to balance environmental sustainability with economic growth, as resource exploitation has increased GHG emissions and hindered climate action. While renewable energy adoption and technological advancements are crucial for reducing pollution, overuse of natural resources remains a concern. The authors advocate for investments in human capital, enhanced environmental regulations, and decreased reliance on non-renewable resources. Despite these challenges, Mercosur countries are committed to sustainable development, aligning their policies with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

7. BRICS

The emergence of BRICS as a coalition of major emerging economies presents a significant challenge for NATO, especially with Turkey's interest in joining the bloc. As BRICS expands its influence, it aims to create an alternative to Western dominance in global governance, which could undermine NATO's strategic cohesion and lead to potential divisions among its members. The collective economic and demographic power of BRICS may shift global dynamics, prompting NATO to reassess its strategies and alliances in a multipolar world. This evolving landscape requires NATO to adopt a nuanced approach to maintain its relevance and effectiveness in an increasingly complex international environment. As this transformation unfolds, the implications for NATO's operational and strategic frameworks could be profound, necessitating a recalibration of priorities.

The rising influence of BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) presents a distinct challenge to Western-led institutions like NATO. While NATO remains anchored in military security and collective defense, BRICS advocates for a multilateral order focused on climate change, sustainable development, and equitable growth for the Global South. This divergence in priorities creates inherent tension, as BRICS frequently critiques NATO's Western-centric approach. To mitigate this friction and ensure global stability, NATO must move beyond mere recognition of BRICS's role and actively seek engagement that aligns with the coalition's developmental and inclusive priorities.

The formation of the BRICS alliance has emerged as a significant challenge for NATO in the current global geopolitical landscape. As a collective of leading emerging economies, BRICS is actively shaping the international order in ways that often diverge from the traditional Western-led framework promoted by NATO (Ruppel & Ruppel-Schlichting, 2013). A key challenge posed by BRICS to NATO lies in its advocacy for a multipolar world order. The BRICS nations consistently push for a more inclusive and equitable global governance system, emphasizing a more balanced distribution of power among various regional and economic blocs. This stands in stark contrast to NATO's historical role as a transatlantic security alliance, which has primarily focused on maintaining Western hegemony in the post-Cold War era. The differing priorities and approaches of BRICS and NATO highlight the complexities of contemporary international relations

and the shifting dynamics of global power, urging NATO to rethink its strategies to engage with these emerging powers constructively.

Furthermore, BRICS has been proactive in establishing alternative financial and economic institutions, including the New Development Bank and the Contingent Reserve Arrangement, which serve as counterweights to the Western-dominated International Monetary Fund and World Bank (Denisov et al., 2019). This shift in the global economic architecture challenges NATO's influence and the centrality of the West in international affairs, as it offers developing nations more options for financial support and investment, reducing reliance on traditional Western institutions. This emerging economic framework not only empowers BRICS nations but also underscores the potential for a redefined global economic order, one that could further complicate NATO's strategic landscape.

Additionally, the BRICS alliance has adopted a distinct approach to global issues, such as climate change and sustainable development, which often contrasts with NATO's traditional policy priorities. While NATO primarily focuses on military readiness and geopolitical stability, BRICS emphasizes the importance of addressing socio-economic factors that contribute to global instability, including environmental sustainability. This divergence in priorities can lead to tensions between the two blocs, particularly in international forums where differing strategies may clash over resource allocation and responses to global challenges. The increasing prominence of BRICS in shaping international discussions reflects a broader demand for a more equitable and representative global governance framework, urging NATO to adapt and engage more constructively with these emerging coalitions to address shared global challenges effectively.

Figure 7: BRICS

Source: <https://www.metropoles.com/brasil/brasil-assume-presidencia-dos-brics-em-2025-veja-o-que-esperar>

BRICS embodies the intersection of Realist and Constructivist dynamics: materially, it functions as a coalition counterbalancing Western hegemony; ideationally, it forges a narrative of South-South solidarity that legitimizes its alternative governance model. In practice, this interplay between material resistance and normative aspiration strengthens BRICS' cohesion, enabling it to challenge the West not only through resources but through meaning.

WORLD WAR III OR A COLD WAR REDUX: EVALUATING GLOBAL RISKS

The emerging U.S.– China rivalry reflects both Realist and Constructivist dynamics. Realists interpret it as a classic power transition struggle between a dominant and a rising state, while Constructivists emphasize the role of competing political identities and governance models. The resulting hybrid confrontation blends economic interdependence with ideological competition, a pattern that recalls aspects of the original Cold War but within a multipolar system

As Carafano et al. (2023, p. 16–20) argues, there are some striking similarities and differences between the current tensions with China and the initial Cold War. The United States and the Soviet Union were the main enemies during the first Cold War, with the Soviet Union being a military rival but not an economic one. On the other hand, the U.S. and China are currently engaged in a rivalry where China has emerged as a significant economic powerhouse and a military one that is modernizing quickly. Even though both wars are fought on a worldwide scale, the contemporary Cold War is distinguished by its emphasis on economic coercion and influence rather than direct military conflict and its economic interconnectedness. The competition in technology has also changed, including fields like cybersecurity and artificial intelligence. Even while the ideological gap between democracy and authoritarianism still exists, there are new obstacles brought about by the advanced technical landscape and the interconnected global economy that call for a nuanced strategy to keep things stable and prevent confrontation. This understanding of the complexities surrounding U.S.-China relations helps contextualize the broader implications for global stability.

Alperovitch (2024) claims that Xi Jinping and President Joe Biden openly oppose the idea of a new Cold War between the United States and China, prioritizing collaboration above hostilities. Still, there are many parallels between the contemporary geopolitical environment and the original Cold War, as both superpowers compete for supremacy in the military, economic, and technical spheres worldwide. With some major exceptions, like a strong degree of economic interdependence, the dynamics of Cold War I are echoed in this new era of armaments races, increased espionage, and space competition. Rather than existential dangers, the strategic contest between the United States and China is centered on worldwide influence. To handle this intricate struggle and avert possible war, the United States must strengthen its advantages and strategic allies. Thus, while leaders may publicly downplay the rivalry, the underlying tensions remain potent and influential in shaping policies and alliances.

Technology and cyberwarfare are crucial in the context of a possible Cold War II with China, as noted by Carafano et al. (2023, p. 17 and 53). One of the main issues is the rampant theft of intellectual property in China, which hinders innovation and favors the Communist Party militarily and economically. By using cyberwarfare to threaten American national infrastructure, China aspires to become the dominant force in cutting-edge fields like artificial intelligence and quantum computing. Furthermore, the military uses of China's biotechnology advancements may have an effect on international security. Geopolitical objectives are achieved through economic pressure and influence, making it necessary for the United States to safeguard its economy and diversify its technological base. In order to counter these threats and fortify the global technology infra-

structure, collaboration with allies is essential. This highlights the importance of technology not only as a tool for competition but also as a potential flashpoint for conflict, necessitating strategic cooperation among allies to navigate these complex challenges.

Evers (2024) contends that, as part of a larger strategy to contain Chinese dominance, the United States has put restrictions on China's access to sophisticated semiconductors. Experts contend that the plan is unlikely to succeed in spite of these efforts. American companies oppose export prohibitions, and China is quickly developing its own semiconductor sector with significant government funding and subsidies. American companies dominate high-value design in the global semiconductor value chain, while Chinese companies handle lower-value assembly. Difficulties facing the U.S. plan include business pushback and slower domestic manufacturing, as well as the Science Act and CHIPS. The Biden administration may need to reevaluate its strategy in order to succeed, striking a balance between the needs of global business and home industry support. The challenges posed by economic interdependence illustrate the intricacies of navigating U.S.-China relations, where economic strategies must be carefully calibrated to avoid unintended consequences that could further entrench competition.

The emerging U.S.-China rivalry reflects both Realist and Constructivist logics: Realist in its struggle for strategic dominance and resource control; Constructivist in the way each power constructs a distinct worldview—liberal democracy versus authoritarian efficiency—to justify its actions. Thus, the confrontation is not only a material contest but a battle over norms and legitimacy, echoing the ideological foundations of the original Cold War, as noted by Carafano et al. (2023, p. 20 and 23).

The United States and China have a close economic relationship, which makes isolation tactics more difficult, and China's trade policies give rise to worries about unfair trade practices and intellectual property theft. Both countries are engaged in a strong competition to preserve technological supremacy in developing fields like artificial intelligence (AI) and quantum computing. From an ideological perspective, they stand for diametrically opposed systems autarky vs democracy and compete for control over international norms and governance. China strategically attacks U.S. interests through intellectual exchanges and economic pressure, therefore the country needs a strong plan to protect its competitive advantage and standing in the world. This ideological struggle further complicates the geopolitical landscape, as both nations seek to leverage their respective strengths in technology and trade to secure influence over global governance structures.

While some commentators (e.g., Hughes, 2024) advance controversial claims about a so-called 'technocratic coup' led by global elites, such arguments remain marginal within international relations scholarship. Mainstream IR debates focus instead on structural dynamics U.S.-China rivalry, nuclear deterrence, cyberwarfare, and institutional fragmentation as the central drivers of a potential Cold War redux. Thus, fringe theories reflect public anxieties about globalization but add little explanatory value compared to established realist and constructivist analyses.

The World War III scenario is represented in the graph below, which shows the alliances and relationships between the transnational ruling elite, as well as their goal of establishing technocratic control over the majority of people on Earth. This depiction emphasizes the interconnectiveness of global power dynamics, illustrating how the tensions between the U.S. and China are not only a matter of bilateral relations but are influenced by broader structural issues that reflect a deepening global crisis. The complexities of these relationships require careful navigation and strategic foresight to avoid escalating conflicts into larger global confrontations. In light of these factors, it becomes evident that understanding the multifaceted interactions between technology, economics, and political ideologies is crucial for formulating effective responses to the challenges posed by the current international landscape.

Graph 1: WWIII scenario

World War III Scenario: Control and Influence Network

Source: Developed by the author

Beyond scholarly analysis, various public narratives have emerged that interpret contemporary crises as evidence of a coordinated global technocracy or elite-controlled world order. Such interpretations, while widespread in media and public debate, fall outside the mainstream of international relations research. They reveal societal anxiety over globalization and technological governance rather than empirically verifiable state strategies.

Hughes (2024, p. 23–24) observes that, in the case of a third world war, the transnational ruling class, distinguished by its extraordinary wealth and its hold over vital societal sectors, covertly targets the global majority in order to construct a worldwide technocracy that is supervised by cutting-edge technology and surveillance. The Global Power Elite from America and Europe, comprising the richest 10% of the population, businesses, and international institutions like the WHO, IMF, and WEF, are important participants in this scheme. This small but powerful group aims to maintain control over humanity, and should their true objectives be discovered, they risk igniting a worldwide revolution. They utilize deceit and misinformation to stay in power, reflecting a broader struggle for influence that transcends national borders and highlights the interconnectedness of political and economic systems.

As Scott (2024) reports, former United States Chief of Staff General Sir Patrick Sanders cautions NATO members that we are living in the most hazardous time since 1945 and calls for more investment in weapons. He names Iran, China, and Russia as the "new axis powers," suggesting they could be even more dangerous than the Nazis in 1939. If nothing is done, he believes a third world war could break out in five years. To avert war, Sanders emphasizes that NATO must update its armed capabilities and close any capacity deficiencies. His warnings resonate with Hughes's concerns about the elite's manipulation of global crises, suggesting that the military strategies pursued by nations are intertwined with the larger narratives constructed by the ruling class to maintain power.

Hughes (2024) acknowledges that the World War III scenario recognizes socio-political and economic factors reflecting transnational class strife as catalysts for global conflict. These factors include the inability of the "War on Terror" to control social movements, indications of a 2019 financial system collapse, a crisis in mainstream media credibility, and the "Covid-19" operation, which served as a cover for biosecurity and psychological warfare. Historical analogies are drawn between the use of global wars to enact drastic reforms and the transition to technocratic rule. This analysis underscores that contemporary conflicts are not merely military in nature but are deeply rooted in societal structures and inequalities, challenging the notion that traditional warfare is the only path to conflict resolution.

Kampeas (2024) writes that after a three-year hiatus, former President Donald Trump and Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu reconciled amicably. During their meeting at Mar-a-Lago, Trump criticized the Biden administration, claiming it has pushed the world toward potential major conflicts, including a Third World War. Trump highlighted his past support for Israel, citing achievements such as the Abraham Accords and the recognition of Jerusalem as Israel's capital. The meeting was cordial, with Trump and Netanyahu expressing mutual support despite previous disagreements. If re-elected, Trump promised to bring peace to the Middle East. This engagement suggests how international relations are influenced by individual leaders' decisions, reflecting a potential shift in alliances and strategies that could either exacerbate or mitigate the risks of broader conflict.

Ragomo (2024) states that headlines express concern over the rising tensions between Israel and Iran, raising the possibility of a third world war. However, World War III is not a distant threat

but a reality manifesting as irregular, low-intensity battles. Today's warfare includes drone strikes, covert operations, and proxy wars, undermining international peace and security. This shift is evident in the Israeli-Palestinian and Syrian conflicts, where resolutions are complicated by regional and international powers. Similarly, the "war on terror" involves covert alliances that foster instability. This widespread conflict is also visible in South Asia, Yemen, Ukraine, the South China Sea, and the Korean peninsula. As countries like Switzerland and Sweden become involved in global disputes, traditional neutrality is eroding. The evolving nature of warfare and conflict dynamics highlighted by Rakgomo reinforces the urgency for diplomatic efforts to resolve tensions, emphasizing that proactive engagement rather than reactive military responses may be critical to avoiding a larger conflict.

According to VOA News (2024), in the wake of recent Chinese naval drills nearby, Taiwan's defense ministry discovered a record 66 Chinese military aircraft circling the island in a 24-hour period. Tensions over Taiwan's sovereignty are at an all-time high, and this spike in Chinese military action includes 56 planes crossing the median line across the Taiwan Strait. Beijing has promised to use force if necessary and regards Taiwan as part of its territory. The augmentation of military presence aligns with recent political happenings, such as a meeting between Taiwanese President Lai Ching-te and Washington's new de facto ambassador to Taiwan. The Chinese aircraft activity is indicative of ongoing regional tensions, especially disputes in the South China Sea, and comes after a similar high in May. This situation exemplifies the precarious balance of power in the region, highlighting the need for strategic diplomacy and the potential for military escalation, echoing the concerns raised by Hughes and Scott regarding the role of elite interests in shaping the geopolitical landscape.

Comparative Insights

1- New Cold War tendencies: Europe (NATO vs Russia), Asia (U.S.-China), BRICS (counterweight to West): The global order is witnessing the resurgence of great power rivalries that echo Cold War dynamics, though the 21st century system is marked by multipolar competition rather than a simple bipolar structure. This new landscape is shaped by regional alliances, economic interdependence, and conflicts in domains like cyber and technological warfare. The tensions between NATO and Russia in Europe, the strategic rivalry between the United States and China in Asia, and the emergence of BRICS as a counterweight to Western-led governance collectively illustrate the crystallization of what can be termed "New Cold War tendencies." These contests highlight both realist concerns over power balancing and constructivist debates about identity and institutional legitimacy.

The confrontation in Europe most vividly revives classical Cold War traits, including military buildups, nuclear signaling, and starkly competing narratives. Since the end of the Cold War, NATO's transformation and enlargement, welcoming states in Central and Eastern Europe, has been perceived by Moscow as a direct encroachment on its sphere of influence (Väyrynen, 2003). Critical turning points, such as the 2014 annexation of Crimea and the full-scale invasion of Ukraine

in 2022, reflect classic security dilemma dynamics. NATO has reinforced its eastern flank and expanded, framing these actions as necessary deterrence, while Russia portrays its own aggression as a defensive move against Western encirclement. This standoff, extending into hybrid domains like energy politics and disinformation, remains central to the European security landscape, underpinned by profound mistrust and escalation risks reminiscent of earlier Cold War psychology (Deutsch, 1983).

In contrast, the United States and China are engaged in a hybrid Cold War that combines intense military competition with deep economic interdependence. China's rise, through rapid military modernization, the Belt and Road Initiative, and technological advances, has positioned it as a comprehensive challenger to American dominance in Asia (Carafano et al., 2023). The most volatile flashpoint is Taiwan, where Chinese military exercises, including record intrusions into its air defense identification zone (VOA, 2024), underscore Beijing's determination. For Washington, Taiwan represents a critical test of credibility and the security of vital technological supply chains. This rivalry extends into techno-nationalism, with restrictions on semiconductor exports (Evers, 2024) and a race for supremacy in artificial intelligence and cyberwarfare. Unlike Europe's more binary divide, Asia is multipolar, with ASEAN states often pursuing hedging strategies that rely on Chinese economic benefits while seeking American security guarantees (Pelaudeix, 2023), creating a less rigid but potentially more unstable environment.

Functioning as an institutional and economic counterweight, the BRICS coalition engages in a soft Cold War against Western dominance. It challenges the financial monopoly of institutions like the IMF and World Bank by offering alternatives through its New Development Bank (Denisov et al., 2019), while its promotion of multipolarity and global governance reform appeals to a broad base of non-aligned states. This creates a fundamental divergence from Western alliances like NATO, pitting a vision of development and South-South cooperation against a traditional security-first agenda (Ruppel & Ruppel-Schlichting, 2013). Therefore, despite its internal challenges, BRICS's collective weight ensures it remains a credible and influential pole in the emerging multipolar system.

The three distinct yet overlapping contests collectively define the contemporary geopolitical landscape. They each challenge the Western-led international order, whether through direct military confrontation, strategic and economic rivalry, or the creation of systemic alternatives. From the NATO expansion that triggered a realist security dilemma with Russia, to the militarization of the Taiwan Strait, and the institutional challenge posed by BRICS, these rivalries share a common impetus: they are all accelerating the decline of the post-Cold War era of United States unipolarity and reinforcing the inexorable drift toward a more complex and contested multipolar world.

Regionalism's dual nature is evident across these cases. Realist dynamics—sovereignty, rivalry, and material constraints—underscore the potential for fragmentation, exemplified by Brexit and Mercosur. In contrast, Constructivist factors of shared identity and norms provide the glue for cooperation in frameworks like ASEAN and the AU. The composite picture shows that regionalism is neither inherently stabilizing nor conflict-producing; its character is instead contingent on the specific interplay of power and identity within a given region.

2- Cooperative tendencies: AU (peace missions), ASEAN (consensus), Mercosur (economic integration):

In an international landscape often dominated by narratives of great power rivalry and emerging cold wars, the persistent and stabilizing force of cooperative regionalism offers a critical counterpoint. Regional alliances are not inherently conflictual; they can also function as essential mechanisms for managing security, fostering diplomacy, and promoting economic development. This cooperative dimension is powerfully illustrated by three distinct regional bodies: the African Union (AU) with its pioneering peace missions, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) through its commitment to consensus based diplomacy, and Mercosur as a driver of economic integration in South America. Together, they demonstrate how regional organizations can counterbalance global tensions and contribute to a more stable, multipolar world order by addressing shared challenges through collective action.

The African Union represents a robust model of regional security cooperation, fundamentally oriented around the principle of "non indifference." This doctrinal shift from its predecessor's strict non interference policy empowers the AU to intervene in grave circumstances such as genocide and crimes against humanity (Gelot & Söderbaum, 2024). This mandate is operationalized through its African Peace and Security Architecture (APSA), an institutional framework designed to manage conflicts on the continent. Through APSA, the AU has authorized and deployed numerous peace missions, from the initial mission in Burundi to the long standing engagement in Somalia. These operations reflect a commitment to "African solutions to African problems," fostering regional ownership in stabilization and mediation efforts, such as its crucial role in facilitating the 2022 truce in Ethiopia. However, this cooperative ambition is tempered by significant challenges, including a heavy reliance on external funding from partners like the European Union and political divisions among major member states that can hamper decisive action. Despite these limitations, the AU exemplifies a cooperative regional model where states pool sovereignty to confront shared security threats directly.

In contrast to the AU's direct security focus, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations has cultivated a distinctive form of cooperative regionalism rooted in diplomatic process rather than military intervention. The foundational "ASEAN Way" prioritizes principles of consensus, consultation, and non interference, creating a unique normative framework for international relations in a highly diverse region (Acharya, 2014). This consensus model ensures that all member states, regardless of size or power, have a voice, thereby preventing the domination by larger powers and fostering a gradual, dialogue based approach to conflict prevention. This has been instrumental in maintaining general peace among members and provides the foundation for broader ASEAN led forums, such as the East Asia Summit, which bring major external powers like the United States and China to the table. In this capacity, ASEAN performs a critical "hedging" function, allowing its members to navigate U.S. China strategic rivalry while maintaining a collective, neutral front (Pelaudeix, 2023). The primary constraint of this model is its often slow decision making, as seen in challenges formulating a unified response to the Myanmar crisis, revealing the inherent trade off between inclusivity and operational efficacy.

Whereas ASEAN's cooperation is diplomatically centered and the AU's is security focused, Mer-

cosur exemplifies the power of economic integration as a vehicle for regional stability and identity formation. Established to transform historical rivalries, particularly between Argentina and Brazil, into productive interdependence, Mercosur's primary achievements are economic and political. The creation of a Common External Tariff and a significant increase in intra bloc trade have woven the economies of member states together, making conflict less conceivable and less economically viable. Beyond commerce, Mercosur has developed a strong political dimension, notably through its Ushuaia Protocol, a democracy clause that allows for the suspension of members who experience a rupture in democratic order. This commitment to shared political values, alongside institutional mechanisms like the Structural Convergence Fund (FOCEM) to address development asymmetries, fosters a tangible sense of South American solidarity. Constructivist scholars would argue that Mercosur has been instrumental in building a cooperative regional identity, thereby reducing the likelihood of interstate conflict. Nevertheless, the bloc contends with persistent internal tensions, such as Brazil's economic dominance and divergent national trade policies, which have stalled ambitious external agreements like the long pending trade deal with the European Union.

A comparative analysis of these three organizations reveals both shared cooperative logics and critical divergences shaped by their regional contexts. All three serve as institutionalized platforms for dialogue, whether through the AU's Peace and Security Council, ASEAN's ministerial meetings, or Mercosur's Common Market Council. Each has also consciously fostered a collective identity—from "African solutions" to the "ASEAN Way" and South American solidarity—that reinforces internal cohesion and amplifies their voice on the global stage. Their differences, however, are equally telling. The AU's focus on hard security through peace missions reflects the continent's experience with internal armed conflicts and instability. While ASEAN demonstrates how consensus and non-interference can sustain regional stability, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) reveals the limitations of similar frameworks when power rivalries dominate. This contrast highlights how the same diplomatic principles yield divergent outcomes depending on political context.

The cooperative tendencies embodied by the AU, ASEAN, and Mercosur provide a vital narrative in understanding contemporary global politics. They demonstrate that regionalism is a multifaceted tool that can be wielded not only for collective defense but also for peacemaking, diplomatic community building, and transformative economic partnership. Despite their distinct challenges—from resource constraints and political divisions to institutional inertia—these organizations underscore the enduring relevance of regional frameworks in mitigating conflict and managing interdependence. Their experiences affirm that the trajectory of international order will be shaped not solely by the contest between great powers but also by the strength of these cooperative mechanisms that build trust, foster integration, and champion dialogue from the ground up.

Taken together, NATO and the EU, the SCO and BRICS, ASEAN, and the AU demonstrate how multipolarity today is shaped less by rigid ideological blocs as in the Cold War—than by fluid, pragmatic coalitions built around security, trade, and identity. Some of these coalitions stabilize

global order by pooling resources (e.g., AU peace missions, ASEAN consensus), while others deepen fragmentation by institutionalizing rival spheres of influence (e.g., NATO vs Russia, BRICS vs Western institutions). This ambivalence lies at the heart of the question posed in this article: whether regionalism today points toward cooperative multipolarity or the seeds of another Cold War.

THE ROLE OF DIPLOMACY, PREVENTIVE DIPLOMACY, AND TRACK II DIPLOMACY

Diplomacy and preventive diplomacy are essential for maintaining international peace and security. Key organizations such as the United Nations, NATO, and BRICS significantly contribute to these efforts. The United Nations Charter emphasizes the organization's main goal of preserving peace through collective, peaceful, and preventive measures, including taking effective actions to prevent threats and address acts of aggression (Mani, 2009). This foundational principle underlines the necessity for global collaboration to mitigate conflicts before they escalate, thereby fostering a stable international environment.

Using philosophy and religion to promote peace, Tobisawa (2024, p. 4 and 30) outlines a number of strategies for preventing and resolving conflicts. These include proactive preventive diplomacy, which addresses tensions before they escalate, cultural and educational exchanges, direct dialogues with political and social leaders, advocacy for nuclear disarmament, specific peace proposals and political initiatives like the "Hiroshima Action Plan," and international support through multilateral cooperation with organizations like UNESCO. These strategies demonstrate the multifaceted approach required for effective diplomacy, which combines political, cultural, and educational efforts to build trust and reduce tensions between states. The aim is to establish world security and peace, reflecting the interconnected nature of diplomatic efforts.

Between conflict prevention and peacekeeping lies the task of resolving disputes through peaceful means, as detailed in Chapter VI of the UN Charter and expanded in declarations like the Manila Declaration of 1982 and the 1988 Declaration on Threats to International Peace and Security. Effective international peace and security maintenance is crucial not just to prevent armed conflicts, but also to address related issues such as reversing the global arms race, alleviating poverty, protecting human rights, and safeguarding the environment (Boutros - Ghali, 1992). This comprehensive perspective on security highlights that diplomacy must address a wide range of interlinked global challenges, emphasizing the necessity of a holistic approach to peacebuilding.

Tobisawa (2024, pp. 7 and 28) believes that international institutions such as the United Nations (UN) are essential in the prevention and resolution of conflicts within the framework of preventive diplomacy. The UN organizes conferences like the NPT Review Conference, provides a neutral forum for discussion and negotiation, and monitors and reports on potential disputes. It manages public education programs, promotes transparency and confidence-building measures, and oversees the implementation of international treaties and disarmament agreements. This role of the UN is pivotal in fostering a culture of cooperation and dialogue, enabling nations to

work together in addressing the root causes of conflict rather than merely responding to its symptoms.

Successful diplomatic efforts include the Camp David Accords (1978), where U.S. mediation resulted in the first peace treaty between an Arab nation and Israel; the Good Friday Agreement (1998), which established a government with shared authority and ended much of the violence in Northern Ireland; and the Iran Nuclear Deal (2015), a significant agreement between Iran and the P5+1 to prevent Iran from obtaining nuclear weapons, according to Shannoun (2023, p. 215 and 225). On the other hand, instances of unsuccessful diplomatic attempts include the Rwandan Genocide (1994), where global efforts were unable to stop the mass murder of people; the ongoing Syrian Civil War (2011-present), despite multiple peace negotiations; and the Venezuela Crisis (2010s), in which diplomatic attempts failed to resolve the political or humanitarian problems. These contrasting examples illustrate the complexities of diplomacy, highlighting that successful outcomes often depend on timing, the willingness of parties to engage, and the ability to navigate entrenched interests.

Adam (2023, pp. 509–513) discusses how Machiavelli argued that in anarchic societies, governments must balance the use of force and diplomacy to survive and thrive, as demonstrated by his political realism theory. Machiavelli's ideas reflect the 16th-century political context, emphasizing that states must navigate a world devoid of a supreme moral authority or divine guidance through a mix of force and diplomacy. In contrast, Dr. Jane Knight's book **Knowledge Diplomacy** challenges this pessimistic view by exploring how innovation, research, and higher education can enhance international relations without sacrificing moral principles. Knight proposes that knowledge diplomacy—encompassing scientific collaboration and higher education—provides a framework for positive global interactions based on reciprocity and mutual benefit, as opposed to the power-focused approach of traditional diplomacy. This perspective suggests that integrating moral considerations into diplomacy can foster more sustainable and just international relationships.

Prantl and Goh (2022, p. 446 and 463) emphasize that, given the complexity of the twenty-first century, multilateralism is crucial for resolving issues at the regional level. They draw attention to the way non-state actors are gaining power over states and the emergence of multi-actor networks. It is believed that traditional state-centric diplomacy is less effective in addressing global challenges. Addressing global issues like pandemics, peacebuilding, and power competition in Asia requires a multilateral approach. The authors propose using a Strategic Diplomacy (SD) paradigm that avoids zero-sum strategies and involves a variety of stakeholders. This call for a strategic approach aligns with Tobisawa's advocacy for multilateral cooperation, emphasizing that inclusive dialogues are essential for managing the complexities of contemporary global issues.

Tobisawa (2024, p. 7 and 29) examines case studies of diplomatic initiatives that succeeded and failed. A few successful instances are the Helsinki Accords (1975), which reduced tensions throughout Europe; Daisaku Ikeda's private diplomacy with the USSR; and the Good Friday Agreement (1998), which restored peace to Northern Ireland. In contrast, the near-nuclear conflict during the Cuban Missile Crisis, the inability of the League of Nations to handle the Manchu-

rian Crisis, and the ongoing Syrian Civil War serve as examples of unsuccessful attempts at diplomacy. This analysis reinforces the notion that while some diplomatic efforts yield positive outcomes, others highlight the limitations and challenges inherent in international negotiations, underscoring the need for adaptive strategies and continuous engagement.

Shannoun (2023, pp. 216, 224) emphasizes the increasingly critical functions of NGOs and unofficial channels in today's diplomatic arena. Their impact is achieved through direct action (coalition-building, mediation, aid) and normative influence (advocacy, awareness-raising). Yet, their effectiveness is contextual and hampered by structural limitations such as funding constraints and fragmented efforts. The success of initiatives like the International Campaign to Ban Landmines illustrates a key principle: NGOs realize their full potential not in isolation, but through collaboration with state actors. This affirms that contemporary diplomacy requires an inclusive, multi-layered approach, leveraging the unique strengths of diverse actors to address complex global challenges.

Prantl and Goh (2022, pp. 444, 460) chart a fundamental shift in modern diplomacy: the transfer of power to non-state actors and the emergence of multi-actor networks. Here, non-governmental actors (NGAs) excel through their adaptability, innovative approaches, and extensive networks, with their efficacy hinging on interconnectivity and risk management. Nonetheless, their capabilities are supplementary, not substitutive. The conclusion is that diplomacy's future efficacy depends on an inclusive, strategic framework that formally integrates the distinct advantages of both state and non-state entities.

CONCLUSIONS

This study set out to examine whether the reconfiguration of global power and the resurgence of regional alliances indicate an emerging Third World War or a renewed Cold War. Through the combined lenses of Realism and Constructivism, it has shown that the current international system is characterized less by inevitable confrontation than by the coexistence of competition and cooperation within evolving regional frameworks.

The analysis demonstrates that regionalism functions as both a stabilizing and destabilizing force. Institutions such as the European Union, ASEAN, and the African Union contribute to peace-building, interdependence, and diplomatic coordination, thereby reducing the likelihood of direct conflict. Yet, rival blocs such as NATO and BRICS can also harden geopolitical divides, reproducing patterns of mistrust reminiscent of the twentieth century. Whether regionalism prevents or fuels conflict ultimately depends on how states balance power politics with shared identity and norms of legitimacy.

From a theoretical standpoint, integrating Realist and Constructivist perspectives reveals that material power and ideational factors are mutually reinforcing. Military alliances, technological competition, and economic rivalry continue to shape state behavior, but these are interpreted through narratives of security, sovereignty, and collective identity that influence diplomatic choices and perceptions of threat.

To mitigate escalation, inclusive multilateral diplomacy must remain the cornerstone of global governance. Strengthening interregional dialogue, enhancing digital and cyber governance, and reforming global institutions to better represent emerging powers would enhance stability and legitimacy.

Ultimately, the challenge is not merely to avoid another Cold War or world war, but to redesign international cooperation for an era of multipolar complexity—transforming rivalry into a sustainable architecture of peaceful coexistence.

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